

Terpenoids: xxxvii. A New Synthesis of dl- β -Selinene and dl- β -Eudesmol

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trans-8-Methylene-10-methyl-2-decalone has been converted to *trans*-8-methylene-10- β -methyl-2- β -acetyl-decalin by a new five steps synthesis. The easy preparation of this ketone afforded the stereoselective synthesis of β -selinene through Wittig reaction with methylene-phosphorane and of β -eudesmol through Grignard reaction with CH_3MgI .

β -Selinene(I) and β -eudesmol(II) are two important naturally occurring compounds among the many derivatives of eudesmane group of sesquiterpenes¹ and are noteworthy for their role in the stereochemical correlation of terpenes and steroids².

The fact that the carbon framework of β -eudesmol^{3,4} and β -selinene^{5,6} incorporating at the C₄ (eudesmane numbering) an exocyclic methylene group differ only in the substitution pattern of their C₇ isopropyl side chain, led Marshall and his associates⁷ to synthesise them from the common intermediate—*trans*-8-methylene-10-methyl-2-decalone. We prepared the same methylene ketone using the method of Marshall⁷ but this key intermediate was further tailored to accomplish the synthesis of the title compounds through different and somewhat easier steps in contrast to those utilized by the earlier workers.⁷

As a matter of fact, the facile conversion of a keto group into an aldehydic function in high yields through the action of methoxymethylene phosphorane⁸ on a cyclic carbonyl compound, prompted us to apply this procedure to the methylene ketone(III) for the elaboration of C-7 Eudesmane side chain. Thus the ketone(III) reacted readily with methoxymethylene-phosphorane to produce the enolic ether (IV) which was

1. W. Cocker and T. B. H. Mcmurry, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **8**, 181.
2. B. Riniker, J. Kalvoda, D. Arigoni, A. Furst, O. Jeger, A. M. Gold and R. B. Woodward, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 314.
3. W. A. Ayer and W. I. Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3027.
4. H. Bruderer, D. Arigoni and O. Jeger, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **9**, 858.
5. M. Ruzicka and M. Stoll, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1923, **6**, 846.
6. A. S. Bawdker and G. R. Kelkar, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, **21**, 1521.
7. J. A. Marshall, M. T. Mike and R. D. Carroll, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2933.

was transformed to the ethylene ketal(V) by refluxing with ethyleneglycol in benzene using paratoluenesulphonic acid as a catalyst as described by Corey and Nozoe⁸. Deketalization of (V) with 10% HCl in acetone solution⁹ at room temperature provided smoothly *trans*-10-methyl-8-methylene-2-formyl-decalin(VI) which on treatment with methylmagnesium iodide gave the secondary carbinol(VIII). Oxidation of the alcohol(VII) with Jones reagent¹⁰ and subsequent equilibration with sodium-methoxide furnished the stereoselective ketone (VIII). The identity of this compound was established through comparison of its I.R. peaks and melting point of its semicarbazone derivative as reported⁷.

The ketone(VIII) was finally subjected to Wittig reaction with methylenephosphorane in the manner of Corey¹¹ to procure (\pm) β -selinene and by Grignard reaction with CH_3MgI to furnish the racemate of β -eudesmol(II).

EXPERIMENTAL*

trans-10-Methyl-8-methylene-decalone-2(III) : This compound was prepared according to the procedure laid down in the literature⁷.

trans-10-Methyl-8-methylene-2-methoxymethylene decalin(IV) : Methoxymethylene-phosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (3.2 g) in DMSO (32 ml) and methoxymethylene triphenylphosphonium chloride (23 g) in DMSO (64 ml) under nitrogen in the

8. E. J. Corey and Shigeo Nozoe, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 5728.

9. O. P. Vig, S. D. Sharma and Inder Raj, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 183.

10. K. Bowden, I. M. Heilbron, E. R. H. Jones, and B. C. L. Weedon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **39**.

11. E. J. Corey and J. M. Chaykovsky, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.

*M. P. and B. P. are uncorrected. I. R. was taken on Perkin-Elmer Infracord using liquid film, Microanalysis by B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar.

usual way. To this was added ketone (III) (6 g) and the contents were stirred at room temperature for 2 hr. and left overnight. It was poured into crushed ice (150 g) and extracted with pet. ether (40-60°), the extract washed with brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent was followed by chromatography over alumina. The material eluted with pet. ether (40-60°) was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to obtain 5 g (71.4%) of enolic ether (IV), b.p. 135°/2-3 mm; $\eta_D^{26} = 1.5103$. I.R. spectrum showed no absorption in the carbonyl region but bands at 3060, 2900, 1680, 1650, 1440, 1380, 1210, 1110, 1020, 990, 888 and 800 cm^{-1} (Found: C, 81.15; H, 10.38; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ requires C, 81.50; H, 10.75%).

trans-10-*Methyl-8-methylene-2, 1', 1'-ethylenedioxyethyl decalin* (V): A mixture of IV (4.5 g), ethyleneglycol (4.2 g), anhydrous benzene (150 ml) and PTS (100 mg) was refluxed under a Dean and Stark apparatus for 6 hr. After working up in the usual way and solvent evaporation, the product was fractionated to furnish 4.1 g (80.4%) of the methylene ketal (V); b.p. 150-51°/2-3 mm. $\eta_D^{26} = 1.5165$. I.R. showed characteristic bands at 3075, 1650, 890 ($>\text{C} = \text{CH}_2$) and 1090, 1040 cm^{-1} (ketal) (Found: C, 75.81; H, 9.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$: C, 76.22; H, 10.24%).

trans-10-*Methyl-8-methylene-2-formyl decalin* (VI): The ketal (V, 3.8 g) was dissolved in acetone (54.5 ml) and to this was added HCl (10%; 18.2 ml). The contents were stirred at room temperature for 3 hr. followed by work up in the usual manner. Vacuum distillation afforded the sharp smelling aldehyde (VI), b.p. 122-25°/2-3 mm, yield 3.05 g (67%); $\eta_D^{26} = 1.5105$.

I. R. showed characteristic bands at 3075, 1650 and 890 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C} = \text{CH}_2$); 2720 and 1725 cm^{-1} (-CHO) and 1450, 1380 cm^{-1} (C-Me). (Found: C, 80.85; H, 10.37. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$: C, 81.20; H, 10.48%).

trans-10-*Methyl-8-methylene-2, 1'-hydroxyethyl decalin* (VII): Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium (5 g) and methyl iodide (30.0 g) in anhydrous ether (200 ml) in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The reagent was cooled in ice cold water and the aldehyde (VI; 2.5 g) was added dropwise with constant shaking and the contents were left overnight at room temperature. Thereafter it was refluxed for about 2 hr. to complete the reaction. The cooled contents were decomposed with NH_4Cl and worked up as usual. The organic layer was dried and the solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation gave the Carbinol (VII), b.p. 135°/3 mm, yield 1.9 g (72%); $\eta_D^{26} = 1.5265$.

I.R. bands at 3400, 3080, 2960, 1650, 1450, 1385, 1170, 1140, 1060, 1010, 990, 930 and 888 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 80.41; H, 11.43. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$: C, 80.71, H, 11.61%)

trans-10- β -*Methyl-2- β -acetyl decalin* (VIII): The Carbinol (VII) (1.8 g) in acetone (15 ml) at 0° was treated with an excess of (6 ml) standard chromic acid reagent¹⁰. After stirring at 0° for 15 minutes, saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate was added to neutralize an excess of the acid contents and the resulting slurry was thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent was followed by chromatography over alumina. Elution with benzene provided the pure methylene ketone (VIII) which was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 120-122°/4-5 mm; yield 1.2 g (62%).

To be sure about the stereochemistry of this compound, it was heated with methanolic sodium methoxide for several hours and the ketone (VIII) isolated in the usual way.

I. R. spectrum of the compound exhibited bands at 3080, 2900, 1720, 1650, 1475, 1385 and 890 cm^{-1} comparable in all respects to those reported by Marshall *et. al.*⁷. (Found: C, 81.35; H, 10.60. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$: C, 81.5; H, 10.75%).

The *semicarbazone* derivative of the ketone after crystallisation from methanol had m.p. 187-188° (lit.⁷ reports m.p. 189-190°) (Found: N, 15.75. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_3\text{O}$: N, 15.96%).

trans-10-β-Methyl-8-methylene-2-β-isopropenyl decalin (1) (*β-selinene*): Methylene phosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (.22 g) in DMSO (2.5 ml) and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (2 g) in 4 cc of DMSO, in the manner of Corey¹¹. To this was added the methylene ketone (VIII, 0.5 g) in THF (2 ml). The contents were stirred and heated for 2 hr at 40° and left overnight at room temperature. As usual, the material was taken up in pet. ether (40-60°). After drying and solvent removal, the residue was chromatographed over alumina when elution with pet. ether (40-60°) afforded *β-selinene* (I) which was further purified by distillation, b.p. 110-12°/6 mm; yield 400 mg (80%).

The structure of *β-selinene* was confirmed through the direct correspondence of its I.R. spectrum with the published spectra⁷ of *β-selinene*, bands at 3075, 2940, 1769, 1645, 1460, 1380, 1260, 1180, 1120, 1040 and 890 cm^{-1} (Found: C, 87.87; H, 11.55. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}$: C, 88.16, H, 11.84%).

trans-10-β-Methyl-8-methylene-2-β, 1'-methyl-1'-hydroxyethyl decalin (*β-Eudesmol*) II: Grignard reagent was prepared to the exclusion of moisture, from dry magnesium turning (0.25 g), methyl iodide (1.5 g) and anhydrous ether (75 ml). This was cooled in ice cold water and the ketone (VIII, 0.5 g) in anhydrous ether (15 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring during a period of 30 minutes. After the addition was complete, the contents were left overnight at room temperature and thereafter the reaction mixture was refluxed for about an hour to complete the reaction. The cooled contents were decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The organic layer was separated and aqueous phase was extracted many times with ether. The total ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed leaving behind thick liquid which solidified on standing. It was purified by sublimation into shining white solid, m.p. 60-65°.

The structure was established through the exact correspondence⁷ of its I.R. spectrum which showed bands at 3395, 3075, 2925, 1645, 1460, 1380, 1255, 1210, 1170, 1130, 1050, 975, 890, 860 and 825 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 80.65; H, 11.68. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$: C, 81.02; H, 11.79%).

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